

Fact Sheet:

Working with Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander peoples in Research

This fact sheet provides information about culturally responsive and safe ways of working with Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander peoples in research¹.

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The rise of Indigenous research methods and methodologies in recent years has shifted research beyond an acknowledgment of, or inclusion of Indigenous ways of knowing, towards a self-determining research praxis.
- Dudgeon et al., 2020

Ethical conduct in research with Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander peoples

It is important that research with Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander peoples is culturally safe, collaborative, and empowering. Ethical guidelines provide a set of principles to help ensure research is safe, respectful, responsible, high quality, and of benefit to Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander peoples. The NHMRC proposes six core values to apply when working with Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander people and communities, which can be used to guide ethical research [1].

¹ Information in this fact sheet is largely drawn from the NHMRC ethical guidelines, Harfield et al., (2020), and Dudgeon et al., (2020). See the reference list for more details.

Case Study Journey: applying the NHMRC values to conduct culturally safe research with Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander peoples

Research by the Transforming Indigenous Mental Health and Wellbeing team is guided by the NHMRC values and guidelines [1]. Below, we provide some examples as a case study journey for one research project. This project was led by Professor Helen Milroy, and aimed to understand the experiences of Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander peoples when engaging with mainstream mental health services [2].

To ensure **reciprocity**, research must respond to a need or priority that is determined by Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander peoples and communities, ensuring benefits are of value. In our research project, Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander peoples were empowered to set the research agenda. For example, the project was led by Aboriginal researchers and knowledge holders, and the co-design process for questions occurred in close partnership with community-controlled organisations. Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander knowledges and lived experiences were acknowledged through adequate compensation, and authorship on papers.

To ensure **cultural continuity**, the research team established an Aboriginal advisory group, and the research team respected the advisory group's decision regarding how to collect data. For example, the advisory group suggested open-ended questions should be asked within a Yarning circle. This step also ensured **respect** was upheld, as it allowed for culturally relevant forms of knowledge sharing, such as storytelling and drawing, and recognised both the individual and collective contributions of Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander peoples.

Equity was demonstrated through inviting representatives from different communities to contribute to the advisory group, and engaging with this group throughout all steps of the research process (e.g., from project conceptualisation through to interpretation of analysis). We also yarning with Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander peoples who lived in metropolitan and regional areas to co-design an interview schedule.

Finally, to ensure the **spirit and integrity** of the research, non-Indigenous research team members engaged in a Cultural Exchange Program with Aboriginal Elders, which aimed to continuously develop their cultural respect and humility as part of their lifelong learning.

Reflecting a commitment to the value of **responsibility**, the research team presented a summary of the research results to participants. The purpose of this feedback was to ensure the research team had captured the views of participants accurately, to clarify questions and to ensure transparency and trust in the research process.

² Transforming Indigenous Mental Health and Wellbeing project: <https://timhwb.org.au/>

Evaluating the Quality of Research with Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander peoples

Research that impacts Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander peoples and communities must reflect Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander values, priorities, and perspectives. It is important to assess the quality of research and risk for bias from Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander perspectives to ensure benefit and not harm. This harm includes being complicit in the colonisation process and marginalisation of Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander peoples.

Questions to guide your work:

- Did the research respond to a need or priority determined by the community?
- Was community consultation and engagement appropriately inclusive?
- Did the research have Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander peoples' leadership and governance?
- Did Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander peoples and communities have control over the collection and management of research materials and data [3]?

Failure to tailor the research questions, design, analysis, dissemination, and knowledge translation to capture understandings that are specific to Indigenous peoples results in research of limited acceptability and benefit, and potentially harms Indigenous peoples.

- Harfield et al., 2020

Aboriginal Participatory Action Research

There are many empowering Indigenous Research Methodologies which increase Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander voice and self-determination in research. Aboriginal Participatory Action Research (APAR) is a good example of an empowering research methodology [4], and is often used by the TIMHWB team.

The engagement and development of community co-researchers in APAR ensures that it is Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander peoples who are identifying the key issues impacting their communities. Actively involving Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander peoples in research can help to reduce the negative effects of conventional research, promote decolonising practices, and encourage relationships and partnerships which are underpinned by cultural humility and safety. For these reasons, APAR is often favoured over other more mainstream, Western approaches when working with Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander peoples.

Strength-Based Approaches

The TIMHWB team takes a strengths-based approach to research with Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander peoples. For example, rather than focusing on deficits and losses, we shift discussions to strength-based opportunities. This strength-based approach can help to reduce blame and guilt, and can be empowering for Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander peoples. Indeed, in Australia there has been a focus on decolonising the discourse of colonial psychology, and building a strength-based Indigenous psychology [4].

Culturally Safe Terminology

The ways we speak are just as important as the ways we act. Using appropriate and respectful language in research is essential [5].

...as Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander people, we have been reclaiming our right to name ourselves. This right, however, is often undermined by media outlets, academics, governments, and non-Indigenous people who continue to use terms that are inconsistent, incorrect, and inappropriate...

...Using Aboriginal and leaving out 'and Torres Strait Islander' when referring to all First Nations peoples of Australia is disrespectful to all Torres Strait Islander people. I am asking authors to respectfully include us...

...Also, to reduce the word count, some people, organisations, governments, and academic institutions have gone even further and reduced Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander people to the acronym 'ATSI'. Reducing us to a mere acronym for the convenience of a word count is offensive to many Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander peoples...

... if we cannot trust our allies and accomplices to get the simple things right, like appropriate terminology, how can we trust you to work with us on the big stuff?

- Canuto & Finlay (2021)

How to demonstrate inclusive and respectful language [5,6]:

Language to avoid	Language to promote
'Aboriginal' alone is not inclusive of the diversity of cultures in Australia, shortening to 'ATSI' can be seen to lack respect, and 'us vs. them' can be seen as divisive language	Use 'Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander peoples' throughout
Avoid using universalising or homogenising labels. For example, Noongar culture is different to Larrakia or Koori culture	Acknowledge the diversity of Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander communities by using pluralisation for words such as 'peoples' and 'cultures'
Avoid perpetuating deficit or paternalistic language, such 'in need of being rescued', or a 'vulnerable minority'	Acknowledge strengths and resilience
Do not use terms such as 'research on' or 'research for' Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander peoples	Promote mutually respectful relationships, through ' working with ' Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander peoples
	Use appropriate capitalisation , for words such as 'Indigenous', 'Elders', 'Country', 'Traditional Custodians'

Culturally Safe Research

It is important that the research process is culturally safe for Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander peoples. Cultural safety is a journey which ensures true engagement and co-design with Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander communities throughout the entirety of the research project. This includes during the development of the research question, project conceptualisation, data collection, data analysis, interpretation, and dissemination.

To ensure quality and culturally safe research, researchers should embed cultural respect into their practices. Cultural respect can be defined as the “recognition, protection and continued advancement of the inherent rights, cultures and traditions of Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander peoples” [7]. Developing cultural respect is an ongoing, fluid process. It is an ideal that is strived for with continual learning and development, rather than an end point that is ticked off or reached.

Developing cultural respect increases the chance that research will be culturally safe. However, it can only ever be the person who is engaged with the research who can determine whether or not the experience was culturally safe. Cultural safety requires both the researcher and the research system to progress through independent but parallel journeys of learning and development. Through this journey, there is a continuum of development that increases cultural competencies, with the aim of achieving cultural safety.

References & Further Information

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